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TEAM-WORK TRAINING: THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

The growing importance of teamwork in the business world has obliged both companies as well as higher educational centers (universities, business schools, etc.) to invest in a type of training specialized in team work. In particular, it deals with the teaching of certain knowledge, skills and abilities (KSAs) which allows the work teams to be more effective, as Chen et al. (2004) or Ellis et al. (2005) have demonstrated in their research. Along the same lines, Stevens and Campion (1994) classify the KSAs into two groups: those of self-management and interpersonal ones and link them to different company human resource practices - among others, that of training. The aim of the present work, following the path initiated by the previously cited authors, is to study the positive influence of teamwork training on the results of the work teams and, also, to compare the effectiveness of the training aimed at team self-management, and the training centered on the internal processes of these teams, based on interpersonal variables.

In order to verify the previous relationships, an experiment was carried out with students from the second cycle of Business Administration and Management who participated in a strategic decision simulation in teams, offering diverse kinds of teamwork training. The results confirm that training aimed at teaching to work in teams has a positive influence on the performance of the work teams. In particular, greater effectiveness is achieved by those teams trained for the self-management of their tasks than those trained for obtaining interpersonal skills which favor the group processes.

Keywords: Team-work Training, Team Self-management KSAs, Team Interpersonal KSAs, Team Outcomes, Strategic Management Simulations, Learning by Doing.

1. INTRODUCTION

The importance of teamwork is recognized in every area of our daily lives. In particular, it has a special relevance in the world of business, above all, from the 1980's onwards, where competition, market globalisation, innovation and demand fluctuations, among other things, have been growing. This means that many companies' activities have become complex and require the participation of more than one individual: i.e., work teams. This is why leading firms increasingly include the teaching of teamwork in their training programs (Butterfield and Pendengraft, 1996). Likewise, this environment and these companies exert pressure on the higher educational centers – universities and business schools – to introduce teamwork related subjects in their curricula (Pfaff y Huddleston, 2003; Ruiz and Bianey, 2004).

It should be pointed out that not all the work teams obtain good results (Rufus, 1998). On occasion, teamwork has to overcome the many obstacles of coordination, role ambiguity, personal conflict, free-riders, etc. (Pfaff and Huddleston, 2003; Rufus, 1998), which mean that the results are not the ones expected. The need is proposed, therefore, for teaching teams how to improve their performance or, in other words, to improve the skills of the team members so that, subsequently, good group results can be obtained. These team skills do not necessarily have to be innate. As some authors have shown in their research (Chen *et al.*, 2004; Ellis *et al.*, 2005; Stevens and Campion, 1994), the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for working adequately in a team can be learnt.

Nevertheless, teaching how to work in a team is not a simple task. This is due to the fact that it goes beyond the limits of any traditionally based training, given that it not only involves the training of skills which can facilitate group activities but also their internal working. This implies that it is necessary to

accompany the more traditional training methods with innovative didactic techniques similar to those of experimental learning (Chen *et al.*, 2004; Ellis *et al.*, 2005; Johnson and Johnson, 2003), with the aim of offering an integral training of this phenomenon.

The question of teamwork training has been dealt with by numerous researchers, above all in recent years (e.g. Chen *et al.*, 2004; Clarke, 2003; Ellis *et al.*, 2005; Hartenian, 2003; Rufus, 1998). It would seem possible, then, to teach the skills necessary for working effectively in a team. In particular, Stevens and Campion (1994) propose teaching two types of KSAs: the self-management team and the interpersonal team. However, we have not found any works which study in depth the different training methods in relation to the KSAs to be learnt.

With the object of studying in greater depth such an interesting and, at the same time, complex subject, the twin aim of our study is: "to study the effect that the teamwork training has on the outcomes of the work teams and, additionally, to compare the effects on group results of two types of training: that aimed at the team self-management and that centered on improving the interpersonal skills of team members".

The present work is structured in four parts: the first is devoted to the training for teamwork teaching and its modalities, proposing the general hypothesis and sub-hypothesis which are the objectives of this study; the second is devoted to describing the methodology developed by means of an experiment, as well as the variables and measurements used; in the third part, we describe the principal empirical results; and, finally, we present the main conclusions, limitations and possible follow-ups to our research.

2. TEAM TRAINING OUTCOMES: SELF-MANAGEMENT TEAM KSAS AND INTERPERSONAL TEAM KSAS

As we have already pointed out in the previous section, the growing complexity of business environments is obliging those educational centers devoted to teaching future business professionals to reexamine their training programs. It is becoming increasingly frequent to include courses devoted to the subject of teamwork. As Ruiz and Bianey (2004) observe, it is a question of preparing "team players" before they join their companies, thus giving the individuals certain advantages over other candidates in the selection processes, as well as over other employees not trained in these aspects (Pfaff and Huddleston, 2003).

Nevertheless, teamwork teaching is not an easy task. It involves the teaching of KSAs of a diverse nature which can facilitate teamwork (Chen *et al.*, 2004; Ellis *et al.*, 2005; Hall, 1999; Hartenian, 2003, among others). For this, it is necessary to employ both traditional didactic methods as well as innovating ones, each one focussed on a type of skill or knowledge. On the one hand, the more traditional methods – by means of text books, videos or classes – can provide the student with concepts and theories regarding the phenomenon. But, on the other hand, the latter should be complemented by other much more attractive ones which pursue the practical application of the theories learnt. In particular, the use of learning-by-doing is gaining adepts, as can be observed in several empirical studies regarding training and teams (Clarke, 2003; Chen *et al.*, 2004; Nulder and Scheppers, 2002; Ruiz and Bianey, 2004). This training aims to get the student (or company worker) to experience, as part of a team, quasi-real situations similar to company reality. Thus, the most frequent active techniques are: simulations by means of personal computers (Ellis *et al.*, 2005; Zantow *et al.*, 2005); the solving of practical cases in teams in the classroom or seminars (Baird *et al.*, 2003; Jennings, 2002) or the participation in group dynamics (Chen *et al.*, 2004; Rufus, 1998).

If we accept the previous arguments, we should broach the question at this time of why it is so important to teach these types of KSAs. The fundamental reason is due to the predictable positive effect on the results of the teams in which the above-mentioned training has been provided and, on the contrary, when members of these work teams have not been trained in these questions. Thus, to verify the good results of this type of training it is necessary, as Peile *et al.* (2001) and Fortune and Utley (2005) observe, to create instruments for evaluating, in some way, the effectiveness or profitability of a specialized team training. Various studies have corroborated the positive influence of this training. On the one hand, Rufus (1998) shows the positive effects of this specialized team training on group tasks and the establishment of

common goals. As Marks *et al.* (2002) corroborate by means of different team experiments, this type of training is positive because it encourages the sharing of mental models among the members of the team and, as a consequence, this carries over into better group performance. Lastly, Ellis *et al.* (2005) obtain revealing results regarding this type of team training, and after submitting various groups to simulation sessions, they show the positive effect of the training programs on planning skills and the coordination of group tasks, of problem resolution and team communication.

However, in other studies, conclusive results have not been obtained concerning this relationship. This is the case with Ruiz and Bianey (2004) who try to show that training improves the effectiveness and skills of the team, but they fail to obtain significant results regarding training, although they do demonstrate the improvement of the team members' skills.

With this in mind, it would appear that team members can be taught to be better team players and to obtain improved group results and, that for this, the key is to attend training programs specialized in these aspects. However, although there exists ample literature about the link between team training and results, authors such as Stevens y Campion (1994) call for new empirical studies which push forward our knowledge boundaries in this field. This invites us to continue studying the subject more deeply, by means of new empirical studies in the area.

From the previous arguments, we can deduce the general hypothesis which we hope to verify in the present paper which links positively the training for the teaching of teamwork with the results or performance of the work teams.

H₁: "Teamwork training improves the results of the work teams"

As we have previously pointed out, our aim is to go one step further. Having accepted the diversity of the KSAs necessary for working well in a team, we propose different training methods in terms of the typology of KSAs to be taught. For this, we rely on the taxonomy of KSAs offered by the previously cited authors, who differentiate between those of team self-management (for adequately developing group activities) and interpersonal ones (for encouraging the internal processes of the group) and opt for two specializations within the teamwork teaching: self-management team training and interpersonal team training. We would expect that the training method selected has an influence, in some way, on the team performance, giving rise to a breakdown of the general hypothesis of the research in two sub-hypotheses, each focussed on a training typology for teamwork teaching.

Within the first training typology (devoted to team self-management) the teaching of two types of KSAs will be included: *the planning and coordination of group tasks and the setting of group objectives*, so that the team members have a significant control over the direction and execution of their group activities (Goodman *et al.*, 1988, *cit. Stevens and Campion:514*). On the one hand, we have to teach the teams to integrate their individual actions, synchronizing and coordinating them, and, for this, it is necessary to learn to plan how to distribute the work, when it will be carried out, and what specialists are at our disposal, etc. (Chen *et al.* 2004, Ellis *et al.*, 2005; Hartenian, 2003; Johnson and Johnson, 2003; Rufus, 1998; Stevens and Campion, 1994). The type of teaching methodology which can be applied in these cases combines both traditional methods – master classes, videos or the reading of manuals – as well as methods aimed at learning-by-doing, above all, by means of group dynamics or the solving of real cases. Some empirical studies regarding training have concentrated more on the self-management KSAs. On the one hand, Gibson (2001) focuses on training aimed at teaching the setting of objectives, not only individually, but also at the team level, achieving good results for the teams which have received training. Ellis *et al.* (2005) show that training exerts a positive effect on planning and the coordination of tasks, while Rufus (1998) shows the positive effect of teamwork training in the case of the task and the objectives.

The previous arguments mean that we can expect a positive effect between the training aimed at self-management and the team results, which we can summarize in the following sub-hypothesis:

H_{1a}: "The training aimed at teaching self-management knowledge, skills and abilities improve the results of the work teams"

Within the second training category, interpersonal aspects would be taught which facilitate the internal processes of the groups and, therefore, the possible causes of some improved group results. These refer to the personal relationships between the members of the group or, in other words, to the ability to maintain working relationships and to interact with other individuals as far as ideas, emotions and different points of view are concerned.

In particular, it is essential to teach some of the most important KSAs which are, of course, interrelated: *creativity, interdependence, internal communication, leadership, the solving of problems and conflict resolution*. The training aimed at interdependence attempts to teach the team members cooperative behavior as opposed to competitive and individualistic traits, given that the actions of each person will condition the results of the group (Johnson and Johnson, 2003; Rufus, 1998). The training aimed at internal communication attempts to encourage the channeling of information and learning within the group, by overcoming the numerous barriers which may obstruct it (Ellis et al., 2005; Hartenian, 2003; Johnson and Johnson, 2003; Rufus, 1998; Stevens and Campion, 1994). The training focussed on the teaching of creativity tries to promote innovation and the creation of ideas in the group as a way of improving or solving problems (Gilson et al., 2005; Johnson and Johnson, 2003; Smolensky and Kleiner, 1995). The training centered on leadership emphasizes the description of who the group leaders are or the teaching of how to become one, as well as promoting more democratic approaches, as opposed to more authoritarian behavior (Johnson and Johnson, 2003; Rufus, 1998). The training devoted to problem solving (a key factor in the work teams) looks to teach the individuals of the team to be able to confront difficult situations which the team might encounter by encouraging the participation of everybody in order to solve them and trying to overcome the majority of the obstacles (Chen et al., 2003; Denton, 1995; Ellis et al., 2005; Hartenian, 2003; Johnson and Johnson, 2003; McCahon et al., 1996; McFadzean, 2002; Stevens and Campion, 1994). Finally, the training aimed at improving conflict resolution, concentrates on ensuring that members learn to draw positive lessons from the conflicts which arise within the team by identifying the type, source or degree of the conflict and insisting on negotiation as the way to resolving any conflicts (Chen et al., 2003; Clarke, 2003; Ellis et al., 2005; Hartenian, 2003; Janssen et al., 1999; Johnson and Johnson, 2003, Stevens and Campion, 1994). Although these types of interpersonal KSAs can be taught by traditional methods, in reality, the most active methodologies are the ones which allow the students to familiarize themselves with them. Thus, it is customary to use computer simulations or group dynamics to encourage the teams to experiment.

With regard to the previously mentioned KSAs, various empirically based studies have been carried out. This is the case with Mitchell and Silver (1990) who show a positive link between these types of skills and teamwork outcomes. For their part, May and Kahnweiler (2000) focus on the training of interpersonal skills for supervisors and managers, achieving a positive effect on learning as long as these are active and participatory training programs. Along the same lines, but concentrating on conflict resolution, it is worth mentioning the work of Clarke (2003), who also shows the positive effect of training by means of an experimental methodology. Equally, Ruiz and Bianey (2004) consider that it is necessary to insist on this type of training for improving team results, as they demonstrate in their work. At the same time, Michalisin et al. (2004) highlight the importance of team cohesion as an essential factor in the achievement of good team outcomes. Focussing on the leadership variable, Wing (2005) evidences the positive effect of having good leaders on team results and the fact that, for this, it is fundamental to teach how to be one. Finally, Ellis et al. (2005) obtain results which corroborate the positive effect of this type of training on two particular variables essential for the team: the internal communication and problem solving.

Thus, from the preceding literature, we now propose a second hypothesis, in this case focussed on the influence of training aimed at the interpersonal KSAs of the team members on the team outcomes:

H_{1b}: "The training aimed at teaching interpersonal knowledge, skills and abilities improves the results of the work teams"

3. METHODOLOGY

With the aim of verifying the general hypothesis and the sub-hypothesis of this paper, we decided to develop the empirical work by means of an experimental methodology. We wanted to evaluate whether certain management teams, within the context of higher university teaching, achieve better results as a consequence of receiving (or not) specialized training in teamwork and, in particular, in their two modalities: self-management and interpersonal. Firstly, we will describe the quasi-experiment by means of a strategic decision simulator. Then, we will explain on the teamwork training programs developed and, finally, we will include the main variables and measurements used in the study.

3.1. The quasi-experiment: The strategic decision simulator

The goal of the study required the setting up of a situation which could be controlled by the researchers. Thus, in line with numerous research works which have used a similar methodology (Argote *et al.*, 1995; Devadas and Argote, 1995; Edmonson, 1999; Espinosa, 2002; Kraut *et al.*, 2002, Michalisin *et al.*, 2004), we proceeded to the preparation of a quasi-experiment.

The experiment was performed with students from the second cycle of their degree in Business Administration, enrolled in the subject of Strategic Business Management. This group was chosen for empirical verification for various reasons: they were students from the second cycle of a degree in Business Administration and Management and, therefore, they would soon qualify as future company managers and would have to work in a team; the second cycle of a degree can be compared to the masters courses in business schools, and the universities and these schools are the principal organizations responsible for training future managers who can work in teams. Students enrolled in the Strategic Business Management course were chosen, given that it is one of the keys to teaching them to be a manager, conceptually, at least. They had to participate in some activities which required working in teams, in particular a strategic decision simulator. We consider this sample of students to be sufficiently representative of students of the second cycle of Business Administration from any country and institution of higher education. The physical place where the experiment was performed was isolated from this environment.

The practice was proposed completely voluntarily with the aim of encouraging a spirit of openness in the rest of the members of the team and the taking of decisions in a dynamic and unpredictable environment (Gopinath and Sawyer, 1999; Marsick and Kasl, 1997). At the same time, the objective was to highlight the importance of learning and innovation (Marsick and Kasl, 1997) and so we avoided any formal evaluation of the simulation and the students were informed that the complete performance of the experiment would only be evaluated positively and qualitatively for the final grading of the subject previously mentioned.

Following the recommendations of Paulus *et al.* (2001) we work with teams in which there were no more than five members, four being the recommended number of members, since it was considered the optimum size for the practice. According to these authors the teams should be formed of the minimum number of members. In this way, potential opportunistic behavior among the members of the team is minimized and team learning is maximized.

The experiment started at the beginning of the 2005/2006 academic year (4th October, 2005) with 87 students taking part, although initially there were 100, divided into 27 work teams (of 3, 4 or 5 members). Furthermore, so that the results were easier to interpret and understand, we grouped the whole of the participating teams in different industries, each one comprising a total of 5 or 6 teams. In this way, one team did not compete against the remaining 26, but rather against the 4 or 5 which formed part of their same industry. Additionally, in the interests of preventing successful strategies from being repeated, the teachers defined certain competitive conditions for each of the industries – annual variations in demand, interest rates, exchange rates, tariffs, etc.–which were appreciably different. This added a certain specificity to each sector, even though these conditions did not come into force until the second decision.

To make the experiment more realistic, a widely proven strategic management simulation computer program was used, developed by the strategy teachers Thompson and Stappenbeck (1999), called *Business Strategy Game 6.0.* and marketed by the publisher McGraw-Hill Irwin.

Each experiment confronted the students with the management and running of a multinational enterprise devoted to the highly competitive business of sports shoes, which made it necessary for them to adopt strategic decisions related to the different areas of the company – production and logistics, investment and financing, commercialization and market research and human resources. Furthermore, each experiment allowed competition between the participating teams, all of them being sports shoe firms, and which started from the same initial position, both internally and externally.

The students who participated in the experiment had to take five decisions, with a week between each of them. The introduction of the data in the computer program was carried out every Friday afternoon for two hours in the computer classroom of the Business School of the University of Valladolid under the supervision of the course lecturers. During this time those doubts were resolved which did not involve the supply of any strategic information. Once the decisions had been taken by the teams, the teachers processed the information and it was sent by e-mail to those responsible for each team who, in turn, forwarded it to their team mates.

3.2. Teamwork training

In line with numerous studies based on experimental methodology, whether applied to teams (Chen *et al.*, 2004; Clarke, 2003; Ellis *et al.*, 2005; Gibson, 2001; Rufus, 1998; Ruiz and Bianey, 2004), or to questions of the training of the company employees (Kozlowski *et al.*, 2001), we sought with this experiment to analyze the influence of training on the outcomes of the teams.

Of the total of 27 teams participating in the simulator, a classification into three groups was made in order to perform the experiment and observe the isolated effect of the training and of the two training methods under study: self-management and interpersonal.

1. *Teams which did not receive teamwork training:* they were a total of 27 students in 9 teams. They devoted themselves to attending the simulations, in their different sessions, but did not receive any type of training which would teach them how to work in teams.
2. *Teams which received training for self-management KSA:* they were a total of 21 students in 6 teams. They attended the simulation sessions, but previously they had received four training sessions, each one of two hours. They used reading materials about companies which have utilized teams, practical cases for team solution, group dynamics focussed on task planning and coordination and the setting of group objectives. At the same time, there was constant interaction with the lecturers who supervised the sessions, for all of which an appropriate classroom was used for this type of dynamics. The basic teaching material was Grant's (2004) case manual, Thompson and Stappenbeck's (1999) business strategy simulation manual and the group dynamics book by Johnson y Johnson (2003).
3. *Teams which received interpersonal KSA training:* they were a total of 39 students grouped in 12 teams. They attended the simulation sessions, but previously they had received a seminary based on group dynamics concerning the following interpersonal skills: problem solving, conflict resolution, internal communication, leadership, interdependence and creativity. All the sessions took place over two hours, giving the students basic documentation and, above all, with diverse practical activities which allowed them to apply the theoretical aspects. The backup book used to develop the sessions was the previously cited manual by Johnson and Johnson (2003).

3.3. Variables

Dependent variable. Team outcomes.

The outcome variable used was the *ranking* (Thompson and Stappenbeck, 1999). The ranking variable is calculated as a weighted mean of the values of the following variables: sales revenues, after-tax earnings,

return on equity, debt rating, the market value of the company and overall evaluation of the strategy (1) (this evaluation is calculated with information regarding the product lines, the quality, the company image, costs, the market share, the price in relation to the competition and the reach of their products. To confirm the robustness of our model, the after-interest and after-tax profits were used as a measurement (*In BDII*).

Independent variable. Training.

With the aim of evaluating the differences between the group which was given training and the rest, various *dummy* variables were introduced.

- *TRAIN1*, with 0 significance: the team didn't receive teamwork training, 1: the team received teamwork training.
- *TRAIN2*, representing the type of training received, with 0 significance: the team didn't receive training oriented towards self-management KSA, 1: the team did receive training oriented towards self-management KSA.
- *TRAIN3*, representing the type of training received, with 0 significance: the team didn't receive training oriented towards interpersonal KSA, 1: the team did receive training oriented towards interpersonal KSA.

Control variables.

The features of the individual are used as control variables, which the literature traditionally considers affect people's learning capacity (Neuman and Wright, 1999; Chen *et al.*, 2004). The information necessary for constructing the variables (which are shown below) was collected before the beginning of the simulation practice – the questionnaires were answered by the 87 students who participated in the simulator (27 teams, divided into 5 industries). See Annex 1 for the questionnaires used.

Specifically, the following characteristics were evaluated:

- The intelligence of the students, measured by means of an IQ test –*INT-* (2) (Mateos Blanco, 2005).
- The personality of the students, measured with a variable by means of Saucier's (1994) cognitive skills' scale, focussing on the emotional stability of the individual –*EMOC-* (3).

At the same time, the motivational aspects of the students were taken into account, given that they have been shown to be relevant in explaining individuals' learning processes (Edmonson *et al.*, 2001; Chen *et al.*, 2004; Ruiz, 2004; Adobor and Daneshfar, 2006). To this end, two variables were employed:

- The attitude of the students which was measured by the attitude to teamwork scale –*ACT-*(4) proposed by Chen *et al.* (2004) (5).
- The perception about teamwork self-efficacy – *UTIL* –(6) which was measured by the scale proposed by Ebby and Dobbins (1997) (7).

Likewise, the individuals' KSAs were measured. The measurement of the KSAs was performed on the basis of the questionnaire consisting of 35 questions designed by Stevens and Campion (1999) who also provided us with it and tabulated the data, since the measurement scales are protected by license. Each question has four possible answers, only one of them being correct (see Annex I for an example of these questions). The results of data tabulation obtained were sent to us via email by the authors of the questionnaire.

- *The KSAs of each individual.* In order to be able to evaluate the initial knowledge of the KSA of each individual –*KSAs-* the students completed the questionnaire before beginning the simulation practice.

4. RESULTS

Below, we present the results of the analysis. Firstly, the initial features of the teams which participated in the simulator are described, with the aim of confirming that no significant differences exist between the three groups – untrained, trained in self-management and with interpersonal training – by means of an analysis of variance (ANOVA). Next, in order to verify our hypothesis, we proceed to carry out a regression analysis using ordinary least squares (OLS).

4.1. Features of the teams

To make sure that the initial conditions of the three groups of students were similar, we proceeded to a one-way ANOVA (on the KSA variable) both at the general level as well as for each one of their modalities: self-management and interpersonal. As can be seen in Table 1, none of the values of the different aspects of the KSAs shows significant discrepancies before the start of the quasi-experiment, which allows us to begin with the two types of training in the groups, with the confidence that the learning which they obtain for teamwork are not the consequence of the existence of a better ex-ante preparation by any group.

TABLE 1: ANOVA OF THE INITIAL KSAs.

Variable	n° obs.	1	2	3	t Test	p Value
KSAs	81	21,64	21,64	20,65	1,01	0,37
Interpersonal KSAs	81	13,80	13,89	12,90	1,11	0,33
Conflic KSAs	81	3,16	3,11	3,00	0,23	0,79
Collaboration KSAs	81	3,88	3,94	3,80	0,05	0,95
Communication KSAs	81	6,76	6,83	6,10	1,26	0,29
Self-Management KSAs	81	7,84	7,75	7,75	0,03	0,97
Planning KSAs	81	3,88	3,97	3,75	0,39	0,68
Setting Objectives KSAs	81	3,96	3,78	4,00	0,42	0,66

We also wanted to verify descriptively and preliminarily that there did exist significant differences in the results achieved by the three groups of students who participated in the simulator (Table 2). As can be observed, the teams which obtained the best results from their participation in the simulator were those with a training oriented to the self-management KSAs, whilst the teams which had no type of training were the ones which obtained the worst results in the simulation. At an intermediary level, as regards results obtained, are the teams whose training was oriented towards the interpersonal KSAs.

TABLE 2. ANOVA OF TRAINING ON THE TEAM RESULTS. (RANKING).

Variables	Teams	Num. students	Mean	F (sig.)
Ranking	No training	27	53,77	60,539 (,000)
	Interpersonal training	39	68,00	
	Self-Management training	21	95,66	
	Total	87	70,26	

Finally, we wanted to confirm whether the groups obtained better or worse results according to the industry in which they had been chosen to compete, given that when we observe the progression followed by the teams, differences can be seen with regard to the results which the teams obtain in each industry throughout the five decisions. However, on carrying out a mean difference analysis, we can observe that

these differences are not significant (Table 3). Therefore, we can assume that the results were not influenced by the industry in which the students competed.

TABLE 3. ANOVA OF TRAINING ON THE TEAM RESULTS. (RANKING).

Variables	Groups	Num.	Mean	F (sig.)
Ranking	Industry 1	15	75,3333	,903 (,466)
	Industry 2	18	74,6667	
	Industry 3	19	65,3158	
	Industry 4	16	71,1250	
	Industry 5	19	66,3158	
	Total	87	70,2644	

Once we have verified the homogeneity of the features of the three groups, we can proceed to verifying the hypotheses proposed.

4.2 Training effects on team results

The OLS regression analysis carried out on a total of 87 students allows us to observe that the features of the team have no influence over the results of the team (Model 1), except the positive effect of the level of intelligence. On introducing into the model the "having received training" variable (TRAIN 1) we see that it has a significant influence on the outcomes which they obtain (Model 2). Therefore, we can consider our *first hypothesis* verified: i.e., training has a positive impact on the results obtained by the team.

TABLE 4. OLS ESTIMATION OF THE TEAMWORK RESULTS VARIABLE (IN RANKING)

Dependent Variable: <i>In ranking</i>	Model 1		Model 2	
	Features of the team + Self-management KSAs training		Features of the team + Interpersonal KSAs training	
	B	t	B	t
C	3,976	6,167***	3,887	7,036***
KSA	0,003	0,242	0,007	0,637
INT	0,017	1,742*	0,011	1,258
ACT	-0,104	-1,013	-0,075	-0,849
UTI	0,164	1,585	0,030	0,326
EMOC	-0,074	-0,927	-0,122	-1,786*
TRAIN1			0,378	5,311***
N	81		81	
F Test (p-value)	1,004 (,421)		5,843 (,000)	
R ²	,251		,567	

Note: ***, **, *, indicate the significance of the parameters to 1%, 5% y 10%, respectively.

The OLS regression analysis, when we introduce the training variable oriented to the self-management KSAs (TRAIN 2), shows that this type of training has a positive and significant effect on the outcomes of the simulator (Model 3). The first sub-hypothesis (H_{1a}) can thus be confirmed.

Finally, in Model 4, the impact of the training oriented towards interpersonal KSAs (TRAIN 3) is estimated. The results, in this last case, do not demonstrate that this type of training has an impact on the team results. Therefore, we can not confirm the veracity of our second sub-hypothesis (H_{1b}).

In the light of the outcomes obtained, it would appear that training is a highly appropriate tool for improving teamwork results. Furthermore, the training oriented towards self-management KSAs is more efficient in relation to the results obtained by the teams. With regard to the control variables used, it can be observed that their impact on the outcomes of the team is very weak and that, excepting the intelligence variable which is a positive influence in Models 1 and 4 and the emotional stability which is a negative factor in Model 2, the rest of the variables are not significant in the analyses.

TABLE 5. OLS ESTIMATION OF THE TEAMWORK RESULTS VARIABLE (IN RANKING)

Dependent Variable: <i>In ranking</i>	Model 3		Model 4	
	Features of the team+ Self-management KSAs training		Features of the team + Interpersonal KSAs training	
	B	t	B	t
C	3,637	7,096***	3,991	6,143***
KSA	0,015	1,381	0,004	0,268
INT	0,012	1,604	0,017	1,750*
ACT	-0,900	-1,113	-0,105	-1,020
UTI	0,003	0,037	0,164	1,581
EMOC	-0,048	-0,759	-0,068	-0,845
TRAIN2	0,480	6,763***		
TRAIN3			-0,028	-0,374
N	81		81	
Test F (p-value)	8,960 (,000)		0,851 (,535)	
R ²	,649		,254	

Note: ***, **, * , indicate the significance of the parameters to 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

5. DISCUSSION

The training aimed at teamwork is continually proliferating in educational programs, both in the universities as well as in business schools and enterprises.

In the present work, and corroborating the results obtained by other researchers (Clarke, 2003; Ellis *et al.*, 2005; Rufus, 1998, among others), we show that teamwork training exerts a positive influence on the results of the work teams. Thus, in our experiment, the performance achieved by the teams which received teamwork training was greater than those not trained in the subject. This should serve as an incentive for continuing this line of research with respect to the teaching of teamwork, in all its different aspects.

However, having studied in depth the training methods proposed, based on the taxonomy of knowledge, skills and abilities (KSAs) - which are fundamental for teamwork - propounded by Stevens and Campion (1994) - we can compare their effects on teams outcomes. It is verified that training aimed at improving group activities by means of self-management has a greater influence on the team results than that aimed at teaching interpersonal KSAs which improve the internal working and the processes of the teams. Perhaps, it is due to the fact that the former obtains results more in the short time, and are more easily noted by the students, than the latter. However, this does not imply that it is not as, or more, important, in an environment like the present one where the key factor is the individual, to consider all the aspects linked to the personal relations - in this case, within the team.

In view of the previous observations, we should draw attention to some of the limitations of this work and the possible follow-up work for remedying this. The first limitation is that the training has only been evaluated in the short term (the 3 months which the simulation sessions lasted). It would be a valuable

experience to lengthen the time span of the study, given that in the majority of the training programs, irrespective of the type of content, the noticeable effects take place in the longer term. The second problem is the non-consideration of other initial team variables which might have a significant effect on performance: for example, the previous personal links between the members of the work team or the greater or lesser state of maturity of the life cycle of the teams. Moreover, when the team results are measured, non-economic measurements of an emotional nature are not considered, as is the case with the team member's satisfaction, something which seems to us an interesting factor to take into account when evaluating the teams.

Research into the complex and fascinating world of teamwork has only just begun. A big effort is now necessary, both by teachers and researchers as well as by practitioners, in order to continue the progress. The implications, in a wide range of fields, are still to be discovered.

6. NOTES

- (1) For further detail concerning the construction of this variable, see the manual by Thompson and Stappenbeck (1999:75-78).
- (2) The final calculation of this variable was carried out by using the instructions of Mateos Blanco (2005). Thus, the total number of correct answers is added up and from this value we subtract the quotient between the errors and the number of options per question minus 1 [Σ correct answers-(Σ errors/options per question -1)].
- (3) The question about the personality of the individuals were added by using the average value on the emotional stability variable (Saucier, 1994).
- (4) The questions were added on a variable using the average value.
- (5) The scales used to measure each of the analysis variables can be seen in Annex I.
- (6) The questions were added on a variable using the average value.
- (7) The scales used to measure each of the analysis variables can be seen in Annex I.

REFERENCES:

- Adobor, H. and Daneshfar, A., "Management simulations: Determining their effectiveness". *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 25 (2), 2006, 151-168.
- Argote, L.; Liang, D. and Moreland, R., "Group versus individual training and group performance: The mediating role of transactive memory". *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, Vol. 21 (4), 384-393.
- Baird, L.; Griffin, D. and Henderson, J., "Time and space: Reframing the training and development agenda". *Human Resource Management*, Vol. 42 (1), 2003, 39-52.
- Butterfield, J. and Pendergraft, N. (1996): "Gaming techniques to Improve the team-formation process". *Team Performance Management*, Vol 2 (4), 1996, 11-20.
- Clarke, J., Experiential learning as enabler to improving conflict management in a work team, Doctoral dissertation, University of Toronto, Canada, 2003.
- Chen, G.; Donahue, L. and Klimoski, R., "Training undergraduates to work in organizational teams". *Academy Management Learning and Education*, Vol. 3 (1), 2004, 27-40.
- Denton, K., "Competence-based Team Management". *Team Performance Management*, Vol. 1 (4), 1995, 5-12.
- Devadas, S. and Argote, L., "Collective learning and forgetting: The effects of turnover and group structure". Paper presented at the *Midwestern Psychological Association Meeting*, Chicago, 1995.
- Eby, L. and Dobbins, G., "Collectivistic orientation in teams: An individual and group-level of analysis". *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 18 (3), 1995, 275-295.
- Edmonson, A., "Psychological safety and learning behaviour in work teams". *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 44 (2), 1999, 350-383.

- Edmonson, A.; Bohmer, R. and Pisaso, G., "Speeding up team learning", *Harvard Business Review*, Vol. 79 (9), 2001, 125-132.
- Ellis, A.; B. Bell; R. Ployhart; J. Hollenbeck and Ilgen, D., "An evaluation of generic teamwork skills training with action teams: Effects on cognitive and skill-based outcomes". *Personnel Psychology*, Vol. 58(3), 2005, 641-672.
- Espinosa, J., Shared mental models and coordination in large-scale, distributed software development, Unpublished Doctoral dissertation, Carnegie Mellon University, Pittsburgh, 2002.
- Fortune, J. Utley, D., "Team progress cheksheet: A study confirmation". *Engineering Management Journal*, Vol. 17 (2), 2005, 21-27.
- Gibson, C., "Me and us: Differential relationships among goal-setting training, efficacy and effectiveness at the individual and team level". *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol 22 (7), 2001, 782-802.
- Gilson, L.; Mathiew, J.; Shalley, C. and Ruddy, T., "Creativity and standarization: Complementary or conflicting drivers of team effectiveness". *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 48(3), 2005, 521-531.
- Gopinath, C. and Sawyer, J., "Exploring the learning from an enterprise simulation". *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 18 (5), 1999, 477-485.
- Grant, R., Cases to accompany contemporary strategy analysis, Blackwell Publishing 5th Edition, Oxford, 2004.
- Hall, J., "Training in teamwork in British university libraries". *Library Management*, Vol. 20 (3), 1999, 149-158.
- Hartenian, L., "Team member, acquisition of team knowledge, skills and abilities". *Team Personnel Management: An International Journal*, Vol. 9 (1-2), 2003, 23-30.
- Janssen, O.; Van de Vliert, E. and Veenstra, C., "How task and person conflict shape the role of positive interdependence in management teams". *Journal of Management*, Vol. 25 (2), 1999, 117-141.
- Jennings, D., "Strategic management: An evaluation of the use of three learning methods". *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 21 (9-10), 2002, 655-665
- Johnson, D.W. and Johnson, F.P., Joining together. Group theory and group skills. Eds. Pearson Allyn & Bacon, Boston, 2003.
- Kraut, R.; Fussell S.; Lerch F. and Espinosa, A., "Coordination in teams: Evidence from a simulated management game". Working paper, Carnegie Mellon University, 2002.
- Kozlowski, S.; Gully, S.; Brown, K.; Salas, E. and Nason, E., "Effects of training goals and goal Orientation traits on multidimensional training outcomes and performance adaptability". *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, Vol. 85 (1), 2001, 1-31.
- Marks, M.; Sabella, M.; Burke, C. and Zaccaro, S., "The impact of cross-training on team effectiveness". *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 87 (1), 2002, 3-13
- Marsick, V. and Kasl, E., "Factors that affect the epistemology of group learning: A research-based analysis". Paper presented at the *Annual Adult Education and Research Conference*, Stillwater, Oklahoma, 1997.
- Mateos Blanco, A., Test psicotécnicos, Tébar, Madrid, 2005.
- May, G. and Kahnweiler, W., "The effect of a mastery practice design on learning and transfer in behavior modeling training". *Personnel Psychology*, Vol. 53 (2), 2000, 353-373.
- McCahon, C.; Rys, M. and K. Ward, K., "The impact of training technique on the difficulty of quality improvement problem solving". *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, Vol. 96 (7), 1996, 24-31.
- McFadzean, E., "Developing and supporting creative problem-solving teams: Part I". *Management Decision*, Vol. 40 (5), 2002, 463-475.
- Michalisin, M.; Karau, S. and Tangpong, C., "The effects of performance and team cohesion on attribution: A longitudinal simulation". *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 57 (10), 2004, 1108-1115.
- Mitchell, T. and Silver, W., "Individual and group goals when workers are interdependent". *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 75 (2), 1990, 185-194.
- Neuman, G. and Wright, J., "Team effectiveness: Beyond skills and cognitive ability", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 84 (3), 1999, 376-389.

- Nulder, U. and Scheepers, H., "Increasing student interaction in learning activities: Using a simulation to learn about project failure and escalation". *Journal of Information Systems Education*, Vol. 12 (4), 2002, 223-232.
- Paulus, P.; Larey, T. and Dzindolet M., "Creativity in groups and teams", in Turner, M.E. (ed.), *Groups at work : Theory and research*, 319-338, Erlbaum, New York, 2001.
- Peile, E.; Easton, G. and Johnson, N., "The year in a training practice: What has lasting value?. Grounded theoretical categories and dimensions from a pilot study". *Medical Teacher*, Vol. 23 (2), 2001, 205-211.
- Pfaff. E. and Huddleston, P., "Does it matter if I hate teamwork? What impacts student attitudes toward teamwork". *Journal of Marketing Education*, Vol. 25 (1), 2003, 37-45
- Rufus, E., *Team building: An isolated view of team dynamics training and its effect on team performance*, Doctoral dissertation, University of Alabama, Huntsville, 1998.
- Ruiz, U. and Bianey, C., *Enhancing teaming skills in engineering students through team training*. Doctoral dissertation, University of Nebraska, Lincoln, 2004.
- Saucier, G., "Mini-Markers: A brief version of Goldberg's unipolar Big-Five markers". *Journal of Personality Assessment*, Vol. 63 (3), 1994, 506-516.
- Smolensky, E. and Kleiner, B., (1995): "How to train people to think creatively". *Management Development Review*, Vol. 8 (6), 1995, 28-33.
- Stevens, M. and Campion, M., (1994): "The knowledge, skill and ability requirements for teamwork: implications for human resource management". *Journal of Management*, Vol. 20 (2), 1994, 503-530.
- Thompson, A. and Stappenbeck, G., *The business strategic game 6.0.*, Irwin McGraw Hill, Boston, 1999.
- Wing, L., "Leadership in high-performance teams: A model for superior team performance". *Team Performance Management*, Vol 11 (1-2), 2005, 4-11.
- Zantow, K.; Kowlonton, D. and Sharp, D., "More than fun and games: Reconsidering the virtues of strategic management simulations". *Academy of Management Learning and Education*, Vol. 4(4), 2005, 451-458.

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